

System of Pre-Competition Technical-Tactical Training of Young Judokas

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Abstract:

The physical abilities of young judokas develop throughout childhood, mainly due to growth and development of puberty. For example, strength abilities begin to manifest themselves in adolescent children due to an increase in muscle mass. Both the aerobic and anaerobic systems gradually strengthen during childhood and adolescence, but the aerobic system develops earlier due to the growth of the circulatory, respiratory and muscular systems. Thus, it is important for the coach to constantly monitor the physical capabilities of young judokas in order to provide more adequate and individualized training loads.

Keywords: SJFT — special judo fitness test, JGST — judo grip strength test, fitness test, physiological abilities, judogi, young judokas, judogi grip strength test.

INTRODUCTION

Endurance is the ability to perform physical work over a short or long period of time without reducing its intensity and effectiveness. The development of endurance is carried out by various training methods. In the process of physical training, it is necessary to solve the following tasks: a) ensure the diversified development of endurance and main muscle groups in order to create the prerequisites for specific manifestations of strength qualities for the successful development of general preparatory, special preparatory and competitive exercises (the so-called general physical training); b) ensure the development of specific and strength abilities (actually strength, speed-strength, strength endurance, strength agility, etc.) necessary for the successful development of motor actions that form the basis of competitive activity in wrestling.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Physical training is aimed at developing physical qualities: endurance, strength, speed, agility and flexibility. The development of dexterity and flexibility occurs in the process of warming up and practicing technical and tactical actions. To develop strength and speed, which in combination give speed-strength qualities and endurance. Finding effective ways to increase the level of general and special endurance and speed-strength abilities in the system of training martial artists is one of the pressing problems. Depending on the conditions of competitive and training activity, endurance and strength abilities become increasingly specialized in the process of their development.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

20 athletes took part in the study. The SJFT is highly correlated with the standing long jump test and the medicine ball throw test. These findings indicate that good performance in SJFT is dependent on high levels of muscle strength in the lower and upper extremities. Moreover, the grip strength test was correlated with the SJFT, indicating that maximal isometric grip strength is also an important factor influencing SJFT performance. Finally, high levels of upper limb muscle strength and hand grip strength are critical to performing JGST.

Young men of later maturation may use aerobic energy sources more efficiently and demonstrate less dependence on anaerobic metabolism than their peers of early maturation [3]. Taking the JGST into account, the results showed that boys who are older, shorter, lighter, slimmer and mature earlier tend to perform well on this test.

Another important issue for coaches is the role of maturation, growth and training experience in specific judo performance (eg SJFT and JGST). It was observed that maturation (assessed by age at maximum speed), judo experience (training), and body fat were significant predictors of SJFT performance [4]. These results highlight that junior judokas who were leaner, matured later, and were more experienced achieved better results in the SJFT. Young men of later maturation may use aerobic energy sources more efficiently and demonstrate less dependence on anaerobic metabolism than their peers of early maturation [2]. Taking the JGST into account, the results showed that boys who are older, shorter, lighter, slimmer and mature earlier tend to perform well on this test.

Table 1 - Predictors of performance of specific tests in judo and the corresponding indicator for young judokas

	R ₂	P	Indicator	Standard odds (β)
SJFT (n)	0.23	0.001	Training	0.34
JGST (s)	0.42	<0.001	Chronological age	1.95
			Maturity	-1.79
			Height	-1.78
			Body mass	-0.34
			Body fat	-0.33

CONCLUSION

- Strength capabilities of the upper and lower extremities are associated with the performance of specific judo tasks (SJFT and JGST) in young judokas;
- Judo maturity, growth, and experience are significant predictors of performance in the SJFT and JGST;
- It is recommended that junior judokas maintain lower levels of body fat, as it is a negative predictor of performance and is also harmful to health;

- Coaches can use simple and accessible tests (eg, standing long jump, medicine ball throws, and handgrip strength tests) to monitor physical performance and monitor training effects in youth judokas;
- SJFT and JGST are good alternatives for accessing specific results of judokas, especially given the difficulty of obtaining a uniform index of results during judo competitions.

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